

GLOBALIZATION'S NEGATIVE IMPACT ON THE MATURITY OF YOUNG
PEOPLE AND MEASURES TO PREVENT THEM.

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada bugungi dunyoning globallashuv jarayoni, uni vujudga keltiruvchi omillari haqida fikr yuritilgan . Bundan tashqari globallashuvning ijobiy va salbiy oqibatlari, uning yoshlar dunyoqarashiga ta'siri haqida ham alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *globallashuv, fikr, dunyoqarash, madaniyat, kamolot, meros, vatanparvarlik, siyosat, mafkura.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена процессу глобализации мира и его факторам. Кроме того, подчеркиваются позитивные и негативные последствия глобализации и ее влияние на мировоззрение молодежи.*

Ключевые слова: *глобализация, мысль, мировоззрение, культура, зрелость, наследие, патриотизм, политика, идеология.*

Annotation: *The article focuses on the globalization process of today's world and its factors. In addition, the article highlights the positive and negative consequences of globalization and its impact on the world outlook.*

Key words: *globalization, thought, outlook, culture, maturity, heritage, patriotism, politics, ideology.*

Introduction: Globalization is derived from the Latin word glob, meaning "roundabout", French in general and in Latin "globe" on Earth. Globalization is being discussed today by scholars, politicians, journalists and entrepreneurs in all countries. First of all, globalization is the result of human progress and global integration of society. Ideas for understanding the essence of globalization are diverse, and the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, said: "... globalization is a dramatic acceleration of life."¹⁴

Basic part: At present, globalization and the process are described in many ways. The term globalization was first used by an American scientist T.Levitt in an article published in the 1983 Harvard Business Revue magazine as a factor in the economic change in the early 80s of the 20th century.¹⁵

In fact, globalization has existed since the second half of the 20th century on various levels and appearances, and this process has come to our forefront. Uzbek

¹⁴ I.A.Karimov "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" -T.Manaviyat 2008, B.111

¹⁵ <http://library.ziyonet.uz/uzc/book/download/98277>

people are also in the process of globalization. the attitude of our people to the globalization process can be explained by the following words of the famous Indian scientist Mahatma Gandhi: I can not always tighten the doors and doors of my house because I have to enter a fresh air. I do not want the weather to turn into a hurricane and destroy my house. "¹⁶

Globalization suffers considerably for the spirituality. Of course, these processes can not be overlooked. It's up to us to take measures to prevent it and to take measures to combat it regardless of the level of the problem.

In this regard, the head of state said: "Someone describes it as a high-tech time, someone is thinking of the age of thinking, another is a mass media. Of course, in all these points, there is a certain sense of truth, rational helium. It is natural that every one of them reflects the character of today's multifaceted and diverse life. But in the minds of many people, this period is a period of globalization. "

Indeed, the globalization process is getting faster and deeper into our lives now. Globalization can be used for two purposes - good and evil. If the actions of the way of justice serve the development of the state and the society, then the progress that is intended for evil is entirely opposite.

As for threats in the globalization process, it is affecting the spirituality as well as in all areas.

First of all, globalization is a social, political and economic process. It is also a phenomenon that is strongly influenced by the culture of nations. It has been recognized as a positive factor of economic integration in the world and facilitated the effective transformation of the national economy.

However, with the growth of information exchange in the world, he entered the sphere of culture and science. As a result, the spiritual threats that affect the culture of the nation bring new challenges to mankind. We must resist these spiritual and ideological threats that infiltrate our country, especially the youth, with the ideas of individualism and egotentrism. Bebah wealth can create a spirit of respect for our national values and values that can prevent spiritual threats. When it comes to spirituality, it is important to emphasize that it primarily protects the nation, national culture and national lifestyle. Therefore, it is important for people to be highly moral in preventing the spiritual and ideological threats that threaten the national culture of the country in the process of globalization. For this purpose it is necessary to organize spiritual and ideological work in the society on the basis of modern requirements. That is to say, first, protecting the future of the country from various ideological threats; Secondly, to comprehend the exact purpose of spiritual threats; Third, to increase the feeling of indifference, not indifferent to the events around us.

Today's tactic, which seems insignificant to man's spirituality, can also be harmed by the gravitational pull of the information world, which can not be measured in an

¹⁶ "National Independence Bar: a Textbook for the Bachelor of the Republic of Uzbekistan" - T.: "Academy", 2005. B.81

invisible but harmful way. In particular, the impact of the "mass culture" mask on the young people's minds, which is a form of spiritual threat, poses a threat to the development of the country. Especially, juveniles sit in different internet clubs and access pornographic sites, misuse cell phones, and take pictures and movies, all of which can greatly damage the spiritual maturity of the human being. Today, it is necessary to be cautious in such processes in our society, and to start the youth in the right direction. At the same time:

- the formation of immunities against different spiritual threats;
- Providing young people with samples of spiritual heritage regularly;
- It is necessary to conduct explanatory work on the negative impact of mobile phones and computer games on human health, spirituality and consciousness.

Only then will we protect our young people, and also our nation, against the flood of all kinds of evil forces and spiritual threats, which will instill in our hearts loyalty and love for the Motherland.